

Warped low-order modeling of musical tones

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ABSTRACT

Source-filter modeling of musical tones requires a filter model for the spectral envelope of the signal. Since the perceptual frequency resolution is best at low frequencies, frequency warping has been previously shown to improve spectral envelope estimation of audio signals. In this paper, considering low-order modeling for harmonic tones, we investigate the perceptual performance of three warped models which extend the filter models: Linear Prediction Coding (LPC), True-Envelope based Linear Prediction (TE-LPC), and Discrete All-Pole method (DAP). The respective warped methods allow a continuous control of the warping factor, and here we are interested in the perceptual quality of the envelope estimation according to the warping factor for all methods. Results of our listening tests show that the frequency warping which best approximates the Bark scale, does not always give the best results.

1. INTRODUCTION

The *source filter* principle, which is popular in speech coding and synthesis, can also be applied to the harmonic tones of musical instruments (cf. e.g. [1,2]). In its basic version, a periodic excitation, the source, is processed by a filter, which aims to reproduce the spectral envelope of the original tone (cf. e.g. [3]). One benefit of the source-filter model is the possibility to independently vary the fundamental frequency and the spectral shape of the synthetic signal. Furthermore, the parametric representation of the source-filter model allows to reduce the number of parameters, which facilitates the synthesis control.

Here, the aim is to obtain very low-cost real-time simulations. Then, we investigate low-order filters which imitate the shape of the original spectrum of musical instrument tones closely in a perceptual sense. One possible method is the well known Linear Prediction Coding (LPC). Unfortunately, as pointed in [4], this method is suitable for continuous spectra but not for the discrete spectra of harmonic tones. To deal with the problem, the Discrete All-Pole (DAP) modeling method [5] and the TE-LPC method [6] have been proposed, both of which identify the coefficients of an autoregressive filter for a discrete spectrum.

In audio processing, one problem is that these prior methods use a linear frequency scale, which is suboptimal in terms of human perception. The frequency scale can be warped to better match the resolution of the human hearing. It has been proposed in [7–10] to apply the filter identification in a warped scale similar to the Mel scale or the Bark scale. Thanks to this modification, the spectral envelope approximation focuses on the low frequencies, and the details at higher frequencies, which are irrelevant in the perceptual sense, are naturally smoothed.

However, these warped methods increase the real-time simulation complexity and our informal perceptual tests have revealed that frequency warping which fits the Bark scale does not give the best results in all cases. The aim of this paper is the study of the influence of the warping for low-order filter estimations, according to a *warping* factor λ which continuously controls the frequency warping. The quality of the filter models as a function of λ is perceptually evaluated using listening tests.

As a general conclusion, we will observe that for low-order modeling, warping brings only a small perceptual advantage compared to the use of the linear frequency scale, which can even be a better choice in some cases.

This paper is organized as follows: section 2 presents the spectral envelope estimation techniques and their warped versions: WLPC (*Warped LPC*), WTLP (*Warped TE-LPC*), and WDAP (*Warped DAP*). Section 3 discusses the synthesis of test sounds which is based on a harmonic sine model of the periodic part, where the harmonic magnitudes and phases are modified according to the filter approximation. Then, the listening tests and results are presented in section 4, and finally, section 5 concludes this paper. Note that the new methods WLTP and WDAP are proposed in this paper by adapting previous methods to our problem. Additional materials are given in the companion web page¹.

2. LOW-ORDER ENVELOPE MODELING

2.1 Linear Prediction Coding (LPC)

2.1.1 Standard LPC

The LPC of order P consists of the prediction of a signal by a combination of the P past values: $\tilde{x}_n = \sum_{i=1}^P a_i x_{n-i}$. The coefficients $\{a_i\}$ minimize the expectation of the square of the residual $e_n = x_n - \tilde{x}_n$, and they are also the coefficients of the AR filter $H(z) = G/A(z)$ where $A(z) = 1 - \sum_{k=1}^P a_k z^{-k}$ and G is the prediction gain.

¹ <http://www.acoustics.hut.fi/go/smac2013-warping>

This standard method usually uses the autocorrelation sequence r_n of the weighted signal. In [4] it is shown that the optimal a_i 's also maximise the spectral flatness of the residual. Then, the frequency response of the filter $H(z)$, gives an estimation of the spectral envelope of $|X(\omega)|$.

2.1.2 Warped LPC

In [7, 10], it is proposed to realise a frequency mapping replacing z^{-1} by an all-pass filter $D(z)$. Then the Warped LP coefficients can be computed in a similar way by replacing the autocorrelation r_n by a warped correlation c_n .

For practical reasons, first-order all-pass filters are usually used: $D(z) = (1 - \lambda z)/(z - \lambda)$ where the pole λ is the *warping factor*. For example, at a sampling rate $F_s = 44.1$ kHz, $\lambda = 0.756$ leads to a warping close to the Bark scale mapping, cf. [8, 9]. Note that if $\lambda = 0$, then $c_n = r_n$.

2.1.3 LPC and Warped LPC of a discrete spectrum

Unfortunately, one well-known problem persists for discrete spectra, such as periodic signals. In [5] it is proved that the autocorrelation of a discrete spectrum is an aliased version of the original continuous case. Therefore, in the case of a high-order LPC, the estimated spectral envelope fits the whole magnitude spectrum, peaks and valleys, and in the case of low-order LPC, the estimated spectral envelope is attracted by the valleys between the peaks. Some methods deal with this problem, such as the TE-LPC and DAP methods presented below.

2.2 True Envelope based LPC

2.2.1 Standard TE-LPC

Most of cepstrum methods for spectral envelope estimation roughly consist of the filtering of a magnitude spectrum $|X(\omega)|$ by windowing its cepstrum with a mask in low frequencies (cf. e.g. [11]). Since this operation does not solve the problem of discrete spectra, the True Envelope (TE, cf. [12, 13]) iteratively computes the cepstral filtering $H_n(\omega)$ on $G_n(\omega) = \max(|X(\omega)|, H_{n-1}(\omega))$. In other words, at every iteration, the valleys of $|X(\omega)|$ are filled by the previously estimated envelope, then the envelope goes towards a smooth envelope passing close to the peaks.

To convert the TE estimation $H_e(\omega)$ to an AR filter $H(z)$, in [6] it is proposed to apply a standard LPC using the correlation ρ_n given by the inverse DFT of the power spectrum $H_e(\omega)^2$ instead of r_n (cf. sec. 2.1.1).

Note that the TE order is defined by the size of the cepstral mask. In the case of a periodic signal of frequency F_0 , the optimal order is $\hat{o} = 0.5F_s/F_0$ where F_s is the sampling rate, cf. [14]. Concerning the LPC order of the TE-LPC, for high quality applications, it is shown in [15] that the same order \hat{o} gives the best results. In the following, we always use this optimal TE order but in order to have low-order AR filters, the LPC order is chosen to be lower.

2.2.2 Warped TE-LPC

In [16], the Mel-based TE-LPC (also called MTELPC) is proposed to decrease the order using a warping. The es-

timate of the Mel-scaled True Envelope (MTE), with a reduced optimal order $0.15F_s/F_0$, is used to compute the coefficients of a warping filter. However, firstly this method uses a fixed frequency mapping adapted to the Mel scale only, and we want to study different warping scales, secondly its quality cannot outperform the MTE quality which is itself below the TE quality.

In this paper we propose two changes. On the one hand, we use a warping defined by the all-pass filter $D(z)$ with the parameter λ , and on the other hand, this warping is done after the estimation of the TE (normally scaled), done with the optimal order $0.5F_s/F_0$. So, the warped LP coefficients are computed starting from the warped correlation γ_n obtained by an inverse DFT of the power of the warped True Envelope \mathcal{H}_e^2 . With ν the adimensional warped frequency, uniformly spaced in $[0, 2\pi[$, $\mathcal{H}_e(\nu)$ is given by an interpolation of $H_e(\omega)$, using the relation: $\omega(\nu) = \nu - 2 \operatorname{atan}(\lambda \sin \nu / (1 + \lambda \cos \nu))$. In the following, this method is called Warped TE-LPC (WTLP).

2.3 Discrete All-Pole methods

2.3.1 Standard Discrete All-Pole (DAP)

As pointed out in section 2.1.3, for a periodic signal an original spectral envelope is sampled by the harmonics, and its autocorrelation sequence is an aliased version of the original one. In [5] the DAP method is proposed to solve this bias by exploiting the frequency positions and the values of the spectral peaks only. For periodic signals these peaks are the harmonics, but the method is not restricted to harmonic spectra. This method is based on the minimization of the discrete version of the Itakura-Saito distance between the squared spectral envelope measured and estimated at the frequencies ω_m of the M spectral peaks. Then, an iterative minimization of E_{IS} leads to a P -order AR filter $H(z)$, which gives an estimate of the spectral envelope passing through the peaks in ω_m .

2.3.2 Warped DAP

In order to adapt this method to a warped frequency scale, we propose the WDAP method. This new version of the DAP method consists simply of computing the algorithm but replacing the linear frequency positions ω_n of the peaks, by their new frequency positions ν_m in the warped frequency scale, defined by: $\nu_m = -\mathcal{L}D(e^{j\omega_m})$. Note that it is possible because the DAP method does not assume the harmonic structure of the input peaks.

Nervertheless, in some cases the WDAP method can be ill-conditioned, which implies some variations, or ‘‘ripples’’, of the spectral envelope between the peaks. Even if the presented WDAP should not be used for spectral modifications, this paper shows its benefit at least for sound coding.

3. REFERENCE AND TEST SOUND COMPUTATION

The reference and test sounds have been computed from original recordings using a frame-by-frame additive synthesis (cf. [17, 18]). Using a harmonic sine modeling of the signal, the attack and the noisy parts have been isolated

Figure 1. Block diagram of the sound computation.

from the harmonic part. The spectral envelope identification is realised for the harmonic part only. Figure 1 sums up the computation.

Reference sound: Because of the poor tuning of the used files, which come from the IOWA database [19], the fundamental frequency has been shifted in order to have a median value at 261 Hz (C4) for all sounds. Note that the natural vibrato is conserved. Then, the overlap-add synthesis of the harmonic part produces the reference sound by adding the original residual (a static sine synthesis is used for every frame, cf. [20]).

Test sounds: The AR filters $H_n(z)$ have been estimated using the three methods for all frames. Then the estimated spectral envelopes are applied to the test sounds by replacing the peak magnitudes by $|H_n(e^{j\omega_{n,m}})|$ where $\omega_{n,m}$ is the (unchanged) frequency of the harmonic m of the frame n . For the peak phases, first the reference phases are changed to $\pi/2$ and the phases are unwrapped using a shape-invariant method, cf. e.g. [21]. Actually, this quarter cycle dephasing guarantees the centering of the signal avoiding clippings. Finally, $\angle H_n(e^{j\omega_{n,m}})$ is added to the unwrapped phase.

Figure 2 shows some examples of spectral estimations for a frame of the clarinet signal. The spectra and the sound examples of all tones are given in the companion web page.

Simulation of a Warped filter The warped method returns the coefficients of the Warped AR filter $H_w(z) = G/A_w(z)$. To simulate the filter using the linear frequency scale, we can algebraically solve the standard ARMA filter $H(z) = B(z)/A(z) = H_w(D^{-1}(z)) = G/A_w(D^{-1}(z))$. Since the orders of the polynomials A and B are also P , the computation of the warped AR filter is as time consuming as a $2P$ -order standard AR filter. That is why, in the following tests, we also study the quality of the standard methods with an order twice ($2P$ and $\lambda = 0$).

Note that because the (W)LPC methods are highly biased for discrete spectra, we automatically adjusted its level to the reference level using their dBA measure. Without this procedure, the WLPC method is always the worst method.

4. LISTENING TEST

The performances of the WDAP, WLPC, and WTLP methods and their non-warped versions were evaluated with a listening test. The task of the subjects was to compare each test tone against the reference tone.

Figure 2. Spectral envelope estimations for a frame of the clarinet signal. Top fig.: comparison between the 3 methods and the True Envelope estimate, $\lambda = 0.72$ and $P = 8$. Note that the level of the WLPC is increased by equalizing the dBA measure. Bottom fig.: comparison of estimations with different values of λ for the WTLP method ($P = 8$).

Four warping factors were used: 0.27, 0.52, 0.72, and 0.8. Here we fixed the higher warping factor at 0.8, which is higher than 0.756, and we selected 3 other factors relatively uniformly spaced. Figure 4 presents these warpings, and a comparison with: the warping given by $\lambda = 0.756$, the Bark scale of [22] and the Mel scale of [23]. Remark that $\lambda = 0.756$ (for $F_s = 44.1\text{kHz}$) gives the warping closest to the Bark scale in the least-square sense, but as figure 4 shows, it is far from the Mel scale which is commonly used in speech recognition.

Figure 4. Frequency warpings used for the listening test and comparison with the “optimal warping” $\lambda = 0.756$, the Bark scale of [22] and the Mel scale of [23].

Figure 3. Marginal means and the 95% confidence intervals for the (a) clarinet, (b) the flute, (c) the saxophone, and (d) the trombone. The results for the WDAP, WLPC, and WTLP methods are presented with circles, rectangles, and crosses, respectively. The horizontal dashed lines present the performance of the best method without warping. The filter order is 8 unless indicated otherwise.

The filter order for the warped versions was 8, and for the non-warped versions two filter orders, 8 and 16 were used, resulting in six filter order/warping factor combinations. Tones from four musical instruments were included in the test: a clarinet tone, a flute tone, a saxophone tone, and a trombone tone. The fundamental frequency of each tone was 261 Hz (corresponds to the note C4).

4.1 Listening test environment, subjects, and the method

The listening tests were carried out in a sound-insulated listening booth at the Aalto University Department of Signal Processing and Acoustics. The tones were played back with Sennheiser HD 650 circum-aural reference headphones at 64 dBC SPL. The user interface was coded with Matlab. Ten volunteer subjects between 25 and 39 years of age participated in the test. They were personnel of the university, and all had previous experiences in participating in listening tests. None of them reported any hearing defects.

Before the actual test took place the subjects went through a practice test, which provided the subjects a possibility to familiarize themselves with the user interface and a pre-selected set of 20 test sounds representing extremes of the test tones in terms of quality. The actual test consisted of three rounds of 76 trials (three methods, six filter order/warping factor combinations, and four instruments results in $3 \times 4 \times 6 = 72$ trials, and additional 4 reference-reference comparisons as acid tests), and the order of the trials was randomized for each round and each subject. Each trial consisted of a tone pair, the first and second tone being always the reference and the test tone, respectively, separated with 500 ms of silence. The subjects were allowed to listen to the tone pairs twice and then asked to rate the quality of the test tone on a continuous five-step

scale with resolution of 1 decimal place. The anchor points were as specified in the ITU-T BS.1284 standard [24]: Imperceptible (5), Perceptible, but not annoying (4), Slightly annoying (3), Annoying (2), and Very annoying (1).

4.2 Results

The performance of each subject was verified by the acid tests. It was required that the grade resulting from the reference-reference pair comparison should be at least 4 (perceptible, but not annoying) in each case. Based on this analysis 3 subjects were discarded from further analysis.

The results of the listening test were analyzed with a four-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). The method, the filter order/warping factor combination, and the instrument were modeled as fixed effects, while the subject was modeled as a random effect. The assumptions for validity of ANOVA were checked before the analysis. The Shapiro-Wilk test confirmed that the variances were equal ($p > 0.05$), but the normality of residuals could not be confirmed ($p < 0.05$). However, since the linear-mixed effects models have been found to be robust against violations of the assumptions [25], and the distribution was very close to normal, ANOVA test was performed.

ANOVA returned significant effects for the method [$F(2, 1434) = 145.91, p \ll 0.001$], the filter order/warping factor combination [$F(5, 1434) = 144.29, p \ll 0.001$], the instrument [$F(3, 1434) = 164.75, p \ll 0.001$], as well as for the interactions between the method and filter order/warping factor combination [$F(10, 1434) = 21.61, p \ll 0.001$], between the method and the instrument [$F(6, 1434) = 38.77, p \ll 0.001$], between the filter order/warping factor combination and instrument [$F(15, 1434) = 45.18, p \ll 0.001$], and the interaction between all three fixed effects [$F(30, 1434) = 10.10, p \ll 0.001$].

Figure 3 shows the marginal means and the 95% confidence intervals for the interaction between the method, the filter order/warping factor combination, and the instrument. Additionally, the Dunnett’s post hoc test [26] with the significance level of 5% was performed. The figures show the grades as a function of the filter order/warping coefficient combination. The horizontal dashed line shows the best result obtained without warping and with an order 16, and it serves as a reference point showing whether warping brings any advantage (effectively, a non-warped filter of order 16 has the same amount of coefficients as a warped filter of order 8).

In the case of the clarinet, Fig. 3(a) reveals that the WDAP method clearly outperforms all other methods, when the warping factor is 0.8, thus producing the best result. For the flute (Fig. 3(b)), the WDAP method seems to achieve the highest scores, but as the confidence intervals overlap with the WTLP method, no conclusion can be drawn which one of these two methods is the best. In the case of the saxophone in Fig. 3(c) the non-warped versions of the three methods seem to produce the best results, although again the confidence intervals overlap with the results of WDAP and WTLP methods with the warping factors 0.27 and 0.52. For the trombone, warping does not bring any advantage, as can be seen in Fig. 3(d), although the confidence intervals of the case $P = 16$ of the non-warped versions overlap with the WLPC and WTLP methods with warping factor 0.52. All these findings were confirmed with the results of the post hoc test.

4.3 Listeners’ thoughts about the test

All subjects reported that the test was fairly easy, the differences in the test tones were clearly audible, and it was easy to make decisions about the quality. Some subjects noted, however, that in some cases it was hard to apply the given scale, since the differences between the test tones varied. Indeed, some subjects judged artefacts as more severe degradation than changes in timbre, for example, and the others rated these degradations quite the contrary. Many subjects reported also that they used more the bottom of the scale than the top, which is also visible in the results (see Fig. 3).

4.4 Discussion

The results show that the WDAP method is the best or among the best methods in the case of the clarinet, the flute, and the saxophone. For the trombone the results show that warping does not bring any significant advantage. Also in the case of the saxophone this is somewhat questionable, since the non-warped methods with filter order 16 obtain the highest grades. The reason for this is the smooth overall shape of the spectrum. The clarinet has prominent odd harmonics resulting in valleys between adjacent harmonics, which implies that warping brings advantage since more effort is put to low frequencies. The situation is different especially for the trombone that has no prominent formant in the spectrum, as can be seen in Fig. 5.

Usually two major problems occur for high λ values: first, because of the ill-conditioning, especially with the WDAP

Figure 5. Spectral envelope estimations for a frame of the trombone signal. Comparison of estimations with different values of λ for the WDAP method ($P = 8$). The spectra of the other tones are presented in the companion web page.

method, the estimation spectrum can have artificial peaks at low frequencies (cf. Fig. 5). Second, the envelope usually decreases at high frequencies, then the spectral tilt increases with λ because of the frequency “compression” at high frequencies. In this case, as shown in fig. 5, the low-order estimation cannot follow the spectrum and the real envelope is over-estimated. Note that a pre-whitening filter can solve this problem but it usually produces unfitting side effects at low frequencies.

5. CONCLUSION

This article presents a new warped method called the WDAP for modeling the spectral envelope of musical instrument tones. In contrast to the standard DAP method [5], the algorithm is computed by placing the linear frequency points by their warped equivalents. Additionally, we introduced a modified version of the TE-LPC method [6], called the WTLP method, in which warping is realized with an all-pass filter with warping coefficient λ and performed after estimating the TE.

As partial conclusions of the results of the listening tests (cf. fig. 3): first, for low-order filters, it is obvious that it is sometimes preferable to use non-warped methods with a order twice, $P = 16$, rather than warped filters with $P = 8$ which has an equal CPU usage in time simulation. Second, we see that the WLPC, or the LPC, has no benefit compared to the two other tested methods. This observation is not surprising because this method is not adapted to discrete spectra, such as periodic signals. Third, the warping closest to the “optimal warping” in the sense of [8] ($\lambda = 0.756$ with $F_s = 44.1$ kHz) is not always the best one in a perceptual sense, and it is preferable in some cases to use a lower warping factor (cf. e.g. the saxophone in Fig. 4(c)).

For practical reasons, we could not do a detailed study with a high number of different instruments, with a higher number of warping factors, and with some different pitches. With 4 instruments and 6 order/warping factor combinations, we got 76 trials and the individual tests lasted almost 45 minutes. Hence, it is difficult to have a general conclusion, nevertheless these tests show that the perceptual optimal warping factor λ depends of the original timbre, or spectral envelope, and is not linked to the Bark scale. Note that the value $\lambda = 0.756$ gives the warping closest to the Bark scale (for $F_s = 44.1$ kHz), and is relatively far from

the Mel scale which is commonly used in speech recognition (cf. Fig. 4). Then, it seems impossible to choose a unique λ , perceptually good for all instruments, in the case of low-order filters.

In next works, it would be interested to derive a objective criterion which allows to choose the best perceptual λ according to the considered instrument.

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